

Tools for intervention design in the CAP Strategic Plans

OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

One of the most important tasks for Member States is to select, design and calibrate the interventions to be included in the national strategic plans, as defined by Reg. 2115/2021 (Art. 109). This is a **controversial task** where **evidence-based decisions can conflict with political interests** and/or stakeholder views. Consequently, political negotiations usually play an important role. In some Member States, the intervention setting has benefitted from policy analyses and public stakeholder engagement, while in others the process was mostly carried out within the political backroom. The **key challenge** is to inform a political process converging to the intervention setting through scientific evidence from robust policy analyses that can strengthen the choices.

MAIN TOOLS ADOPTED: STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Eco-Scheme Farm Simulation tool (NL)

The tool consists of a farm income simulation model that offers insights into the **effect of various eco-scheme activity choices on farm income**. The tool has a twofold objective: (i) to support governments in the design of eco-schemes, and (ii) farmers in the choice of the eco-schemes to apply for. The tool has an accompanying website. **To support governments**, the tool simulates income outcomes under different eco-scheme arrangements, which inform the final design of the eco-schemes. **To support farmers**, the tool allows them to choose from a menu (22+ eco activities) and calculate a performance-related payment per hectare: farmers can simulate different choices and see what per hectare payments they generate. The tool was developed because of the particular eco scheme functioning in the Netherlands, where the eco-scheme payments are based on a point system.

It can support both policymakers in the design phase, and farmers' choice. It is openly available and easy to interpret.

It was specifically tailored to the Dutch case, based on a point system for eco-schemes: it might require relevant adaptations with other eco-scheme systems.

Farm Income calculation tool (NL)

The Farm Income Calculation Tool is based on FADN data and offers insight into the **effect of various policy options on farm income**. The tool has supported the analysis of various policy options, especially direct payments and basic income support, and their potential effect on farm income. The tool takes into account different farm sectors and different farm size classes. Thus, it is relevant mainly in the context of interventions setting.

It is based on a reliable and rich data source available in all Member States, and it is relatively easy to use and interpret.

The analysis is limited to direct payment interventions, and focuses only on income outcomes, without considering environmental and social implications and trade-offs.

Eco-scheme modelling tool (DE)

The tool is based on a sophisticated approach based on three distinct models to **address the multifaceted aspects of eco-scheme design**. It conducts initial evaluations of ecological and economic impacts according to farm size and type, a **projection of the ensuing budget requirements** and, in addition, a specific estimation of the costs associated with farming without chemical-synthetic plant protection products for a year. The models were developed **as part of the ex-ante analysis activities**.

It provides a comprehensive view on the different implications of adopting different eco-schemes.

Different models need to be calibrated to investigate different eco-schemes, whereas results and indications are effective in general scenarios but less in very specific scenarios.

